

Design, Development and Experimental Evaluation of a Vortex Actuation System

Georgios Andrikopoulos
Computer Science, Electrical and
Space Engineering
Luleå University of Technology
Luleå, Sweden
geoand@ltu.se

George Nikolakopoulos
Computer Science, Electrical and
Space Engineering
Luleå University of Technology
Luleå, Sweden
geonik@ltu.se

Abstract— In this article, the potential of utilizing a commercially available Electric Ducted Fan (EDF) as a negative-pressure actuator for adhesion purposes is experimentally tested. To this purpose, a novel EDF-based Vortex Actuation System (VAS) is proposed and presented from a design, development and experimental evaluation perspective. The effect of different EDF design properties and design alterations to the actuation system is analyzed, for providing novel considerations on optimizing the adhesion efficiency of such a system.

Keywords—Electric Ducted Fan, Vortex Actuation, Negative Pressure, Adhesion Force

I. INTRODUCTION

EDFs have been traditionally popular for their utilization as a propulsion method for both big and small-scale aircrafts, mainly due to an increased thrust efficiency by the ducts reduction of tip vortices and the pressure drops at the blade tips [1]. Typical EDF designs, as graphically displayed in Fig. 1, consist of a motor and an impeller, encased by a cylindrical duct and shroud. A rotor and aft cone are incorporated to reduce the turbulence of the air flow through the duct around the motor (Fig. 1(A)), although the aft cone is omitted in cases of high-power motors (Fig. 1(B)).

The EDF's ability to generate a negative pressure and actively adhere to a surface, when their ducted structure is placed at a close proximity [2], [3], has recently led to their integration in Wall-Climbing Robots (WCRs) [4]. Although the WCRs presented in the related literature have been utilizing a number of different methods for adhesion, from passive [5], [6] and active suction cups [7], [8] to vortex chambers [2], [9] and magnetic attraction [10], [11], the use of an EDF-based design as an adhesion method, provides important advantages that could increase the potential usability of WCRs. Specifically, EDFs do not require the adhesion mechanism to be in contact with the target surface, which alleviates the design challenges of adhesion in cases of curved, rough or non-ferromagnetic surfaces [2]. In addition, no external equipment (e.g. compressor, tubes etc.) must be used for maintaining adhesion, which produces an untethered-friendly solution.

In EDF-based designs found in literature, the main research aspect has been either the negative pressure generation [2] or

Fig. 1. Typical EDF designs in assembled and exploded view.

generated thrust [3], [12]. In these cases, the experimental evaluation has been constrained on investigating the effect of the gap, i.e. the distance of the EDF shroud to the target surface, on the adhesion efficiency. Thus, there is an identified gap on the investigation of additional important design parameters, such as the EDF's structural placement, the length and dimensions of the duct, the dimensions of the shroud and its distance from the surface etc..

To this goal, a novel EDF-based Vortex Actuation System (VAS) is proposed for analyzing important properties such as adhesion force, pressure distribution, current draw, motor temperature etc. during the VAS' operation when placed in variable distances from a test surface. The main novelty of this work stems from the development and experimental evaluation of a novel EDF-based Vortex Actuation System (VAS) with the goal of investigating the potential of utilizing commercially available EDFs as vortex actuators and optimizing their adhesion efficiency [1]. The produced results will act as a new knowledge basis on EDF-based designs and a cornerstone for the modeling, identification and control approaches for such actuators, with the goal of incorporating and utilizing the resulting optimized design into WCRs.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. Section II covers the fundamental negative pressure adhesion principles, while Section III presents the conceptual design of the proposed VAS, the selected design variables, the prototype implementation of the setup and the utilized components. In Section IV, the experimental evaluation of the VAS is presented in detail from the prism of the design modifications, while insight is being provided on the system's properties and the optimization of its adhesion efficiency. Finally, the concluding remarks are provided in Sections V.

This work has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Framework Programme under the call FET-OPEN, grant agreement No. 665238.

II. NEGATIVE PRESSURE ADHESION PRINCIPLE

Negative pressure adhesion works on the principle of generating and maintaining a low-pressure zone P_a inside a cavity compared to the surrounding outside pressure P_b . As depicted in Fig. 2, the difference in pressure will induce a force F_s across the projected cavity area onto the target surface, A , by the high-pressure region [13] as:

$$F_s = A(P_b - P_a). \quad (1)$$

Considering an EDF-based adhesion mechanism, the low-pressure zone lies within its shroud, hence the active pressure area is $A = \pi(r_s^2 - r_d^2)$ mm² with r_s and r_d denoting the outer shroud radius and the duct's internal radius, respectively. In this definition, the effect of the shroud's curvature is neglected for simplification purposes, while the area A will from now on be referred to as the active area. In this configuration, an increase in applied force can occur via a decrease in the shroud's pressure, or an increase in the active area. Furthermore, air flow through the low-pressure zone P_a is introduced by the distance between the shroud's end and the test surface, h , as displayed in Fig. 2. The flows Q_{in} and Q_{out} entering and exiting the chamber, respectively, are defined by,

$$Q_{in} = A_{in}u_{in}, \quad Q_{out} = A_{out}u_{out} \quad (2)$$

where A_{in} and A_{out} denote the in- and outlet areas (Fig. 3), while u_{in} and u_{out} denote the air velocity into and out of these areas. The outlet area, also known as Fan Swept Area (FSA), is defined as $A_{out} = \pi(r_d^2 - r_m^2)$ mm², with r_m denoting the radius of the motor's cylindrical case, while the inlet area $A_{in} = 2\pi hr_s$ mm² is proportional to the gap height h and the shroud radius r_s .

For a negative pressure zone to be generated, the flow out of the chamber must be higher than the flow in, for a specific period. As P_a lowers, air is pulled in through the gap and after a time t the flow reaches an equilibrium, with the lower pressure zone being maintained. The steady state operational point is defined as:

$$A_{in}u_{in} = A_{out}u_{out} \quad (3)$$

In addition to the adhesion force produced through the negative pressure, the EDF will generate a thrust as it pulls air through the duct. At small h , the air density will not be enough to create a big thrust force, but as the gap increases and airflow is less restricted, the generated thrust will increase. Ultimately the thrust will converge to its free flight equivalent [14].

III. VAS SETUP DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE COMPONENTS

A. Conceptual Design

One of the main goals for the VAS setup is to be easily adaptable for fitting EDFs of different dimensions and design characteristics. As shown in Fig. 4(A) and (B), the VAS structure is properly modified to incorporate the two typical EDF designs presented in Fig. 1(A) and (B), respectively.

The VAS was mainly designed for measuring the adhesion force F exerted from a test EDF to the test surface. To achieve

Fig. 2. Shroud detail in half-section view with highlighted pressure zones and basic geometrical properties.

Fig. 3. Vortex adhesion operating principle as shown from the half-section view of an EDF, with highlighted geometrical parameters.

this, as represented in Fig. 4, the EDF is mounted to a legged support structure where each of the four legs are connected to the baseplate via a load cell. In this configuration, the total measured force F is derived by the summation of the force measured by the four load cells, displayed in Fig. 4 as $F_{\{1,\dots,4\}}$.

Another design goal of the presented setup was the measurement of the pressure alterations during the VAS's operation, for which the sensing areas of interest had to be defined. Provided the general symmetry of the VAS structure, the flow distribution along circular sections around the EDF's longitudinal axis was assumed to be symmetrical, while the aerodynamic effect of the legged structure was assumed negligible. For these reasons, as presented in Fig. 4, a vacuum sensor array was placed underneath the test surface with the sensing tips placed coincidentally through inlet holes of the surface at equal intervals c and distance r_c from the center point. In this way, the setup provides with a series of surface pressure points, denoted as $P_{\{1,\dots,8\}}$.

To expand the evaluation span of the VAS adhesion properties, different design variables in the setup and modifications to the original EDF structure were incorporated. Specifically, the distance of the test EDF from the test surface h was conceptualized as variable and to this purpose the legged structure was equipped with multiple, inlets placed at predetermined intervals (as shown in Fig. 4(A) and (B)). The legged parts were properly adjusted in height to have the shroud touching the surface when connected to the bottom inlet ($h=0$). In addition, shrouds of different outer radius r_s were designed to be interchangeable via mounting brackets for evaluating the effect of the active surface and volume change on the attraction between the VAS and the test surface for a given distance. For the needs of this study, the shrouds' height l was selected as constant and predefined.

Fig. 4 Graphical representation of the VAS experimental setup for the two EDF designs presented in Fig. 1: (top) side view, (middle) bottom semi-transparent view with highlighted sensor components, (bottom) half-section view with highlighted design variables.

An additional design criterion was the incorporation of a temperature sensor on the VAS motor cover. These temperature measurements could indicate a possible overheating in cases where the motor does not get sufficiently cooled by the generated airflow. Finally, vibration dampeners were incorporated symmetrically around the surface to block the setup's translational motion at high throttle values.

B. VAS Prototype Components

For the needs of this study, two EDFs developed by Hobbyking (under the brand name Dr. MadThrust) were selected for their different specifications, while both being characterised by high-power, high-thrust performance and low weight; all vital characteristics for their potential use in a WCR. The corresponding specifications of both models are presented in Table 1. The Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) selected for both tested EDF units was the Turnigy AE-100A with continuous current capability of 100 A. The pre-built aluminum EDF shroud in both test cases was replaced by four different renditions, which were 3D printed with outer radius r_s = 50, 60, 70 and 80 mm, following an outward curvature profile and constant shroud thickness 2 mm, while all the shroud heights were predefined at $l = 22$ mm.

The VAS prototype, which is displayed in Fig. 5 for both test-EDF cases, was 3D printed from Polylactide (PLA) in Ultimaker 2+ printers following the required design properties for the execution of this study. Specifically, the test surface was printed as a 190×190×2 mm (Length×Width×Height) plate, with incorporated inlet holes for the pressure sensors, as well as mount extrusions for the load cells. In this prototype setup, the gap height h can be set between 0 and 21 mm in 3 mm increments. This was achieved via the inlet holes of the

TABLE I. EDF SPECIFICATIONS FOR THE SELECTED TEST CASES

	(A)	(B)
Material	Aluminium Alloy	Aluminium Alloy
Inner Diameter(mm)	70	92
Duct Thickness(mm)	0.75	0.75
Weight (g)	313	670
Rotor Fan	10 Blade Fan	12 Blade Fan
Motor Type	Brushless DC 2200kV	Brushless DC 1600kV
Max RPM (rpm)	48000	41000
Max Power (W)	1900	2350
Cont. Power (W)	1700	2200
Max Voltage (V)	22.2	22.2
Max Current (A)	76	98
Max Thrust (kg)	2.45	3.80

structure's four legged extrusions (Fig. 5).

For measuring the force F generated from the EDF, four TE Connectivity FX1901 button-type load cells, with 11.34 kg maximum range, were utilized and properly incorporated in the respective leg tips, while the load cell amplifiers selected for these experimental trials were four SparkFun HX711. The acquisition of the negative pressure measurements was achieved via multiple NXP USA Inc. MPXV5050V differential pressure sensors with a sensing range of up to -50 kPa. The sensors were placed radially at a $c = 12.5$ mm interval that was dictated by the sensor dimensions. Also, an Analog TMP37 temperature sensor was properly mounted on the motor case,

Fig. 5. VAS prototype for the two EDF cases with highlighted sensor and data acquisition components.

while custom vibration dampeners were incorporated around the test surface to adequately prevent undesired translational movements during operation. Finally, the acquisition of the setup's sensorial data and the control of the EDF's operation was achieved via two National Instruments USB-6008 cards and two Arduino Mega.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE VAS ADHESION PROPERTIES

A. Shroud and Active Inlet Area Alterations

Initially, for the experimental evaluation of the VAS properties under the two selected EDF cases, multiple trials were performed for different combinations of shroud radius r_s and gap height h values. Force measurements were acquired as the summation of the four load cells $F = \sum F_l, l = 1, \dots, 4$, while subtracting the weight of the VAS acting on the force measurement points. The points $P_n, n = 1, \dots, 8$, denote the vacuum sensors radially and outwards from the surface center, starting with P_1 as the center sensing point. It is important to note that for the variable shroud radii r_s , the sensors lying under the VAS and shroud differ. Specifically, for $r_s = 50, 60, 70$ and 80 mm the sensors $P_{\{1, \dots, 4\}}, P_{\{1, \dots, 5\}}, P_{\{1, \dots, 6\}}$ and $P_{\{1, \dots, 7\}}$ lie within the outer radius, respectively, while in all aforementioned cases, $P_{\{1, \dots, 3\}}$ and $P_{\{1, \dots, 4\}}$ are positioned under the (A) and (B) EDF duct, respectively.

To investigate the force-to-throttle relationship, experimental sequences were repeated for both EDF cases (A-B), gaps $h = 3 - 21$ mm in 3 mm increments and shroud radii $r_s = 50 - 80$ mm in 10 mm increments. The throttle T input signal was selected as a pyramid function of 5 % increments

every 2 seconds, with a peak throttle $T_{\max} = 100$ % and then reversed down in the same manner until reaching $T_{\min} = 0$ %. The obtained experimental results showed that all maximum measurements of negative pressure, force and power were acquired at maximum 100% throttle. For both EDF cases and for the same gap h , an increase in the shroud radius r_s leads to a progressive increase in all maximum values, a phenomenon that can be explained by the increase in the active shroud area A as defined in Section II. An important observation is that although an increase in h , for the same r_s , leads to a significant decrease in the P_n measurements, the adhesion force does not follow the same decreasing behaviour.

As shown in Fig. 6, for both EDFs and all presented cases of different gaps and shrouds the force follows an hysteretic path to the changes in throttle, with the upper and lower branches of the hysteresis loops progressing with throttle increase and decrease respectively. In most cases, the hysteretic nature of this system ranges from 4 – 6 %, while reaching peaks of 20% in cases of $h = 3$ mm. For all shroud radii, the maximum adhesion force appears to increase while h increases, until it reaches a maximum point after which it starts decreasing. The maximum forces for each case were extracted and shown in Table 2, which also highlights the gap value at which that optimum adhesion efficiency is observed.

TABLE II. MAXIMUM ADHESION FORCES AND RESPECTIVE GAPS FOR CASES (A-B) AND DIFFERENT SHROUD RADII.

	$r_s = 50$ mm	$r_s = 60$ mm	$r_s = 70$ mm	$r_s = 80$ mm
(A)	$F = 32.1$ N $h = 9$ mm	$F = 40.7$ N $h = 9$ mm	$F = 46.6$ N $h = 9$ mm	$F = 61.1$ N $h = 6$ mm
(B)	$F = 18.1$ N $h = 21$ mm	$F = 37.2$ N $h = 18$ mm	$F = 51.2$ N $h = 15$ mm	$F = 60.2$ N $h = 15$ mm

An adhesion efficiency comparison shows that case (A) reaches maximum adhesion forces at smaller h than case (B), while those optimum distances decrease with the increase of r_s in both cases. Case (A) is also characterized by larger maximum forces for smaller r_s values (50, 60 mm), while for $r_s = 70$ mm case (B) presents increased efficiency. The maximal forces appear for both EDFs on the largest shroud ($r_s = 80$ mm) and their values are comparable and close to 60 N.

The above observations are also visible in Fig. 7, which displays the maximum mean force measurements extracted for the test EDFs, in relation to the ratio of the inlet and outlet areas $A_{out}/A_{in} = \pi(r_d^2 - r_m^2)/2\pi hr_s$, as defined in Section 3. It can be observed that an increase in r_s leads to an increase in maximum mean forces, which agrees with (1), given the increase in the active area A . For case (A) and for each $r_s = 50, 60, 70$ and 80 mm, the respective maximum increase in F is translated as approximately 30, 66, 90 and 149%, when compared to the free-flight maximum thrust of 24.5 N. For case (B) and considering the high free-flight maximum thrust of 38.0 N, F is showing a decrease of 52 and 2% for $r_s = 50$ and 60 mm, while for $r_s = 70$ and 80 mm it changes to a maximum increase of 34 and 58%, respectively. Also, Fig. 7 reveals a correlation for both EDF cases on their optimal operating points. Specifically, for both EDFs, those maximal forces are acquired when A_{out}/A_{in} converges to 0.8. The knowledge of this value is an important design tool as it provides the ability to predict the optimal gap h for a given EDF and shroud diameter.

Fig. 6 Transition of force F to throttle T hysteresis loops for both EDF cases (A-B), gaps $h = 3$ -21 mm and shroud radii $r_s =$ (a) 50, (b) 60, (c) 70 and (d) 80 mm.

Fig. 7. Maximum measured adhesion forces for throttle $T = 100\%$, in relation to the outlet/inlet active area ratio A_{out}/A_{in} for the two EDF cases (A-B) and the four different shroud radii r_s .

This convergence to the optimal adhesion point is a highly important finding, since it determines the design details of all future prototypes incorporating the VAS, as trade-offs between EDF dimensions, shroud size and gap are introduced. For a given EDF, satisfaction of the ratio A_{out}/A_{in} to the optimal point would mean a decrease in h for an increase in r_s . For a given shroud radius r_s , operating an EDF of smaller A_{out} , which is translated to smaller duct radius r_d or larger motor radius r_m , would mean the need for smaller gap to satisfy a constant A_{out}/A_{in} and generate the optimal performance.

The optimal adhesion force is approximately 60 N for both cases, thus leading the EDF choice down to the overall performance. Case (A) is consuming less power for the same optimal adhesion and its smaller weight (half of case (B)) indirectly increases the optimal performance due to the larger bandwidth. On the other hand, case (B) provides a performance more robust to changes in the gap, which is important for a robotic system that will have compressible components.

The results also revealed a change in pressure distribution relevant to the gap. In an effort to further investigate this phenomenon, the surface pressure distribution P_n with respect

to the radial distance r_c from the surface center, which coincide with the pressure sensor points, for all gap heights h and shroud radii r_s are presented in Fig. 8. These results show an increasing behaviour as the shroud radius increases, with an evident dissipation of the vortex phenomenon and the generation of a ripple-like pressure distribution on the surface points enclosed by the shroud. This change in distribution emphasized by the maximum pressures is rapidly progressing for all shrouds in gaps h between 3 – 9 mm for (A) and 6 – 12 mm for (B), where the increase in h shifts the dominant pressure points from the near-center ones $r_c < 40$ mm to the middle and outer points of $r_c > 40$ mm.

As the gap increases in (A) and (B) and although the overall negative pressure distribution gets minimized, the force undergoes a big increase for specific gap values. This observation leads to the conclusion that the occurring vortex is not the sole factor for adhesion to the test surface. Specifically, the produced thrust results in an additive force component that leads to the observed increase in the measured force summation. Further increase of the gap height would lead to the EDF reaching an adhesion force plateau and generating thrust converging to its free flight equivalent.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this study was the structural optimization of the Electric Ducted Fan's (EDF) adhesion efficiency for its future incorporation in a Wall Climbing Robot (WCR). To this goal, a Vortex Actuation System (VAS) was designed and developed for measuring the pressure distribution and adhesion force generated when an EDF is placed at close proximity to a test surface. Experimental trials were focused on shroud radius and distance from surface (gap), which led to the important observation that an increase in the gap for the same shroud radius leads to a significant decrease in negative pressure, but the force does not follow the same decreasing behaviour.

Fig. 8 Measured pressure P_n distributions for the two EDF cases with relation to the surface radial distance r_c at maximum throttle $T = 100\%$, for gaps $h = 3$ - 21 mm and for shroud radii $r_s =$ (a) 50 , (b) 60 , (c) 70 and (d) 80 mm.

An insight was given on the pressure distribution during the VAS operation in different configurations, where an increasing behavior was observed as the shroud radius increased and indicated a clear change in pressure distribution as the gap altered for both EDF cases. These results showed an evident dissipation of the vortex phenomenon and the generation of a ripple-like pressure distribution on the surface points enclosed by the shroud. This revealed the additive nature of a thrust force component, which was occurring abruptly after exceeding a specific gap threshold and was leading to large increase in adhesion efficiency. The results involving the maximum forces acquired for both EDF cases and all combinations of shroud radius and gaps showed an optimal point of operation, which when compared to the two EDF free-flight maximum thrusts led to a maximum increase of 149% and 58% in exerted force, respectively.

The plotting of forces to the ratio of the inlet and outlet areas of the EDF showed a convergence of optimum performances to the same value for both EDFs. This finding was deemed of particularly high importance, since it determines the design details of all future prototypes incorporating the VAS, as trade-offs between EDF dimensions, shroud size and gap are introduced.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Brusell, G. Andrikopoulos, G. Nikolakopoulos, "Novel Considerations on the Negative Pressure Adhesion of Electric Ducted Fans: An Experimental Study", in 25th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED), 3 – 6 July 2017, Valletta, Malta.
- [2] J. X. J. Xiao, A. Sadegh, M. Elliott, A. Calle, A. Persad, and H. M. C. H. M. Chiu, "Design of Mobile Robots with Wall Climbing Capability," Proceedings, 2005 IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics., pp. 24–28, 2005.
- [3] J. Xiao, B. Li, K. Ushiroda, and Q. Song, "Rise-Rover: A Wall-Climbing Robot with High Reliability and Load-Carrying Capacity," Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics, pp. 2072–2077, 2015.

- [4] A. Brusell, G. Andrikopoulos, G. Nikolakopoulos, "A Survey on Pneumatic Wall-Climbing Robots for Inspection", in 24th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED), 21 – 24 June 2016, Athens, Greece.
- [5] S. Kawasaki and K. Kikuchi, "Development of a Small Legged Wall Climbing Robot with Passive Suction Cups," in The 3rd International Conference on Design Engineering and Science, ICDES 2014, 2014, pp. 112–116.
- [6] Y. Yoshida and S. Ma, "Design of a Wall-Climbing Robot with Passive Suction Cups," 2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics, pp. 1513–1518, 2010.
- [7] J. Shang, T. Sattar, S. Chen, and B. Bridge, "Design of a climbing robot for inspecting aircraft wings and fuselage," Industrial Robot: An International Journal, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 495–502, 2007.
- [8] R. Pack, "A rubber-tuator-based structure-climbing inspection robot," IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, no. April, pp. 1869–1874, 1997.
- [9] Q. Zhou and X. Li, "Design of Wall-climbing Robot Using Electrically Activated Rotational-flow Adsorption Unit," 2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), pp. 5758–5763, 2016.
- [10] Y. Zhang, T. Dodd, K. Atallah, and I. Lyne, "Design and Optimization of Magnetic Wheel for Wall and Ceiling Climbing Robot," 2010 IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation, pp. 1393–1398, 2010.
- [11] Z. Bi, Y. Guan, S. Chen, H. Zhu, and H. Zhang, "A miniature biped wall-climbing robot for inspection of magnetic metal surfaces," 2012 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics (ROBIO), pp. 324–329, 2012.
- [12] P. Sekhar and R. Bhooshan, "Duct Fan Based Wall Climbing Robot for Concrete Surface Crack Inspection," IEEE India Conference (INDICON), 2014.
- [13] Y. Guan, H. Zhu, W. Wu, X. Zhou, L. Jiang, C. Cai, L. Zhang, and H. Zhang, "A Modular Biped Wall-Climbing Robot with High Mobility and Manipulating Function," IEEE/ASME Trans. Mechatronics, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1787–1798, 2013.
- [14] R. A. Sharman, "Electric Ducted Fan theory and practice," 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://www.rcgroups.com/forums/showatt.php?attachmentid=6384145>